

Optimizing AI Inference on Android Devices: A Comparative Study of GPU and NPU Acceleration

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Abstract—The pervasive integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into the Computing Continuum is driving a shift toward decentralized, real-time processing at the Edge. However, achieving autonomous and efficient Edge-Cloud operations requires overcoming significant challenges in performance sustainability and hardware heterogeneity. This paper investigates optimal execution strategies for AI models within the context of intelligent Edge service management, focusing on two critical tasks for infrastructure observability and smart services: object detection (YOLO family) and image classification (ResNet). These configurations evaluate various model quantization schemes and the utilization of on-device accelerators, specifically the GPU and NPU. Our core objective is to empirically determine the combination that achieves the best trade-off between minimal accuracy degradation and maximal inference speed-up.

Key words—Artificial Intelligence, Heterogeneous Computing, GPU, NPU, SoC, Performance, YOLO, ResNet, Android

I. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the *Computing Continuum*, with the expansion of Cloud boundaries toward Fog, Edge, and IoT paradigms, is transforming the deployment of digital solutions in critical sectors. In this post-digital transformation era, the agility and effectiveness of applications depend on dynamic service management capable of reconciling real-time constraints with geo-distributed and massively scalable infrastructures. As Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems transition from research prototypes to large-scale commercial applications, computational cost and energy consumption have become major concerns. The inference phase, where models operate continuously, dominates this consumption. Specifically, according to Google’s estimates, AI-related tasks accounted for 10-15% of its total energy use between 2019 and 2021, with inference consuming 60% of that energy [1]. Similarly, Meta’s internal reports indicate an energy capacity distribution of 10:20:70 for experimentation, training, and inference, respectively [2].

The escalating demands of AI workloads have driven the evolution of computing personal systems away from homogeneous processors toward heterogeneous architectures. This approach integrates multiple processing units, such as CPUs, GPUs, TPUs, and specialized accelerators, within a single system to optimize performance and energy efficiency by assigning tasks to the unit best suited for them.

Furthermore, these advances are critical to the emerging Edge-to-Cloud paradigm [3–6]. In this model, data is processed locally at the “Edge” when possible, optimizing latency and bandwidth, while complex processing is offloaded to the “Cloud”.

In the contemporary mobile computing landscape, AI performance is a core differentiator. The increasing complexity of AI models, pushed by the rapid popularization of AI [7], demands execution that meets strict real-time and accuracy requirements. Initial solutions involved offloading computation to the GPU, but recently approaches has been moved to the use of a specific *Domain-Specific-Architecture* (DSA) as NPUs for this specific task. This DSA is engineered specifically to accelerate the tensor operations that dominate AI model layers, achieving better results in both compute speed and energy efficiency. Along with advancements on hardware, numerous frameworks emerged to allow developers to make use of artificial intelligence in their applications, such as PyTorch, ONNX and TensorFlow. However, when mobile devices became powerful enough, TensorFlow Lite, an extension of TensorFlow with select operations, enabled local execution on the device itself of certain lightweight models. As of 2024, TensorFlow Lite has been rebranded into LiteRT, short for *Lite RunTime*, and in the near future, it will be renewed again to LiteRT Next as Google keeps adding functionality to the framework, with the main focus being native support for accelerator offloading of model operations.

In the context of AI benchmarking, MLPerf [8] has emerged as the industry standard for evaluating Machine Learning (ML) inference across a spectrum of systems, ranging from embedded devices to large-scale data centers. Its primary objective is to provide a framework-agnostic and architecture-neutral evaluation of performance. This paper adopts a methodology aligned with MLPerf principles, tailored specifically for assessing inference performance on commercial Android-based SoCs. To ensure a representative evaluation, we selected two core models from the MLPerf suite that are fundamental to modern computer vision: ResNet [9] for image classification and the YOLO family [10] for object detection. By contrasting these models, we capture both the baseline requirements of classification and the complex, real-time demands of object detection, yielding robust data that reflect the energy-efficiency needs of current mobile applications.

The manuscript is structured as follows: Section II

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describes topics related to the experimentation environment used in this work; Section III describes the methodology for this study; Section IV presents the results obtained, including performance comparisons; and Section VI summarises our contributions and proposes future research directions.

II. ENVIRONMENT

A. Hardware aspects

All the experimentation has been carried out in a stock Android tablet device, namely a Samsung Galaxy Tab S9. This device has been chosen as it comes with a System-of-Chip (SoC) which includes a NPU alongside the GPU and CPU, the devices that will be evaluated in this paper. The specific SoC is a Qualcomm Snapdragon SM8550-AC also referred to as Snapdragon 8 Gen 2 Mobile Platform. There are the three main computing units inside the SoC of interest for this paper, CPU, GPU and NPU, alongside other smaller dedicated units for networking or image processing.

The SoC CPU, named *Kryo*, is made up of eight cores arranged in a big.LITTLE configuration, with five *big* cores and three *little* cores. The name of each one and their maximum frequency is listed in table I. Of those cores, the three *little* ones are ARM Cortex-A510 cores, the first generation of high efficiency cores from the ARMv9 series of processors running at up to 2 GHz. The *big* cores on the other hand are not five of the same type of processor, instead being made up of three different kinds of ARM core, two Cortex-A710, another two Cortex-A715, and finally one Cortex-X3. Of these *big* cores, the X3 stands out as it is the most powerful one of the set reaching up to 3.36 GHz compared to the A7XX cores that run at up to 2.8 GHz.

Table I: Kryo CPU configuration

ID	Type	Frequency (GHz)
0	A510	2.016
1	A510	2.016
2	A510	2.016
3	A710	2.803
4	A710	2.803
5	A715	2.803
6	A715	2.803
7	X3	3.360

In addition to the CPU, the SoC incorporates a dedicated Qualcomm Adreno 740 GPU, supporting single and half floating-point precision execution (GPU16 and GPU32 execution modes), and a dedicated NPU branded by Qualcomm as the Hexagon Processor, capable of executing both integer and half-precision float computations. Publicly available specifications for the GPU architecture are scarce; the only detailed internal information comes from a third-party blogger’s analysis¹. From this analysis, it is deduced that the GPU comprises 12 Shader Processor units running at up to 719 MHz, a configuration also corroborated by internal Android system configuration files.

¹Adreno 740 information Kurnal’s blog

The SoC also includes a dedicated NPU featuring specialized units for tensor, scalar, and vector operations, all connected to a shared internal memory. This shared memory is crucial for reducing data transfer latency between these execution units, as the primary feature of the Hexagon is its ability to utilize Micro Tile Inferencing. This technique involves partitioning the layers of the AI model and dispatching each specific operation (tensor, scalar, or vector) to the corresponding dedicated execution unit for parallel and optimized execution.

Table II: Peak performance summary

Device	Peak Ops
CPU	19.6 GFLOPS
GPU	2.2 TFLOPS
NPU	26 TOPS

Table II summarizes the theoretical peak performance for the three available execution devices. It is important to note that while CPU and GPU figures are expressed in floating-point operations per second (FLOPS), the NPU performance is reported in tera-operations per second (TOPS), reflecting its optimisation for integer-based inference.

B. Software environment

To fully exploit the available heterogeneous hardware resources, developers utilize the LiteRT framework to integrate AI functionalities into their applications. Since LiteRT natively executes *.tflite* models, a mandatory conversion step is required for models originally developed in frameworks like PyTorch. This conversion is performed externally on a host machine before deployment to the target device. The final *tflite* model is obtained via a multi-step pipeline: first, using PyTorch’s export utilities to generate the intermediate *.onnx* format, and subsequently employing Katsuya Hyodo’s *onnx2tf* package for the conversion to *.tflite* target. Although LiteRT offers a direct conversion path via its *ai.edge.torch* package, this feature is still in early development and lacks broad model support; therefore, the *ONNX*-intermediate pipeline was selected. Crucially, the *onnx2tf* toolchain allows for the explicit selection of different model quantization schemes, as summarized in Table III.

Table III: Quantization reference

Name	Datatype			
	I/O	Ops	Acts	Weight
float32	FP32	FP32	FP32	FP32
float16	FP32	FP32	FP32	FP16
int_q	FP32	INT8	INT8	INT8
int_q_int16_act	FP32	INT8	INT16	INT16
full_int_q	INT8	INT8	INT8	INT8
full_int_q_int16_act	INT16	INT8	INT16	INT16
dynamic_range_q	FP32	Mixed	FP32	Mixed

Post-training quantization (PTQ) can be implemented through two primary approaches: static and dynamic quantization. This study primarily employs static quantization, a method where both model weights and activation distributions are converted

to the target data type (e.g., INT8) offline. This results in a model with fixed parameters that are directly used in layer operations, maximizing execution speed. In contrast, Dynamic Quantization (hereafter DYN) utilizes 'dynamic-range operators'² that quantize activations to 8-bit precision at runtime, immediately before computation. While weights are stored in 8-bit format, they are often cast back to floating-point precision during the operation. Although this scheme incurs a slight runtime overhead compared to the static approach, it remains faster than full FP32 execution and typically offers superior accuracy preservation.

Even though many integer widths can be used for operations, weights and activations when saving the model and are actually supported by the *Tensor* class in LiteRT, there are no optimized implementations of operations for 16 bit integers³.

In order to facilitate the experimentation a small Android application has been developed that runs the models and stores inference results and speeds. Starting from LiteRT version 2.0 is planned to change to LiteRT Next, which will make previous applications incompatible due to changes in the API. As of version 2.0.2 of LiteRT, the pipeline to run models in the NPU does not work properly⁴, so for this paper version 1.4 was also needed to be able to use this accelerator.

To successfully evaluate performance across the entire heterogeneous architecture, a mixed framework approach was needed due to software compatibility constraints. Specifically, CPU and GPU workloads were executed using the LiteRT Next API, which offered superior control over these units, while NPU workloads required the use of the more stable standard LiteRT framework. This methodological split allows for the comprehensive benchmarking of each accelerator’s capabilities, as detailed in Table IV.

Table IV: LiteRT version requirements

Device	LiteRT version
CPU	2.0.2
GPU	
NPU	1.4.0

III. METHODOLOGY

The experimental workflow follows a multi-stage model preparation pipeline, as illustrated in Figure 1. Initially, models of various sizes were sourced from their respective official repositories: the PyTorch *torchvision* module⁵ for ResNet, and the Ultralytics platform⁶ for the YOLO family. The conversion process consists of two main steps: first, PyTorch models are exported to the intermediate ONNX format; second, these are converted to the final TFLite (*.tflite*) format using the *onnx2tf* tool. During this

second stage, the models are also quantized. While *onnx2tf* outputs floating-point versions (FP32 and FP16) by default, we configured the tool with specific parameters⁷ to generate the dynamic and integer quantized variants described in Table III.

The benchmarking phase is performed by running inferences against the standard validation datasets corresponding to each model family. Specifically, the ImageNet 1K validation dataset⁸ is used for ResNet family, while COCO⁹ validation dataset is employed for YOLO family. The primary performance data collected includes the average inference time (latency) across the entire dataset and the corresponding accuracy metric. This comprehensive evaluation was repeated for every model size, quantization variant, and target device.

Finally, the last phase involved the quantitative assessment of the obtained classification and detection results to determine model accuracy. For the YOLO models, the most common accuracy metric is mean average precision (mAP) directly obtained from the Python package *pycocotools*. For ResNet, the top-1 percentage metric is also calculated by computing how many of the total predictions recorded match the ground truth for the image class. Figure 1 illustrates the process at a glance.

Fig. 1: Experimental Workflow and Model Preparation Pipeline

IV. RESULTS

Before presenting the results obtained for the ResNet image classification and YOLO object detection models, some observations are necessary. Firstly, the Table V summarizes the acronyms used throughout the following subsections to refer to the precision, device, and quantization variants used in the experiments. Secondly, the FP32-bit model executed on the CPU on a single thread is considered as a baseline which will serve as reference for speed-up and accuracy loss comparisons. And finally, the accuracy metric depends on the model evaluated: Top 1 accuracy for ResNet, and the *mean Average Precision* (mAP) for YOLO.

²Dynamic operators in LiteRT

³LiteRT documentation states lack of INT16 kernels

⁴LiteRT Commit 34682d3

⁵ResNet models in *torchvision*

⁶Ultralytics website

⁷*onnx2tf* documentation

⁸ImageNet 1K validation dataset

⁹COCO validation dataset

Table V: Acronym correspondence

Device	Acronym	Meaning
Device	CPU-SC	Single threaded
	CPU-MC	Multithreaded
	GPU32	FP32 GPU execution
	GPU16	FP16 GPU execution
	NPU	NPU Execution
Quantization	FP32	Floating Point 32 bits
	FP16	Floating Point 16 bits
	INT8	Integer 8 bits
	FINT8	Full Integer 8 bits
	INT16	Integer 16 bits
	FINT16	Full Integer 16 bits
	DYN	Dynamic

A. ResNet

Table VI presents the inference time measured in milliseconds (ms) for the different quantization and device variants. As the data shows, the 16-bit integer variant exhibits very poor performance (high latency), a trend observed even across different model sizes. Therefore, these quantizations are excluded from the analysis for the remainder of this section. Results also show the clear dominance of the NPU as the fastest executing device, followed by the GPU and lastly the CPU.

Table VI: ResNet18 Average inference time (ms)

	CPU-SC	CPU-MC	GPU32	GPU16	NPU
FP32	79.06	26.34	13.68	5.54	1.20
FP16	79.31	26.52	15.71	5.61	1.19
INT8	23.26	5.63	21.77	22.68	0.61
INT16	791.35	798.39	831.95	857.21	882.30
FINT8	23.06	60.36	32.57	32.48	0.51
FINT16	883.34	883.18	883.50	883.16	880.98
DYN	32.31	7.43	40.42	37.14	37.14

Table VII shows the Top-1 classification accuracy observed during ResNet18 model inference, varying the quantization scheme and the target device. Almost all variants achieve satisfactory accuracy, close to 69%. The single notable exception is the FINT8 variant, which reaches a drastically low Top-1 accuracy of only 0.08%. Therefore, this variant is also excluded from the remaining experimentation.

Table VII: ResNet18 Top1 accuracy

	CPU-SC	CPU-MC	GPU32	GPU16	NPU
FP32	68.81	68.81	68.81	68.8	68.82
FP16	68.82	68.82	68.82	68.79	68.81
INT8	65.87	65.87	65.87	65.87	65.96
INT16	65.95	65.95	65.95	65.95	65.95
FINT8	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.08
FINT16	65.95	65.95	65.95	65.95	65.95
DYN	68.71	68.71	68.71	68.71	68.71

Consistent with previous findings, Figure 2 illustrates the inference latency for the ResNet50 model. The NPU delivers superior performance across all variants, achieving a 120 \times speedup compared to the CPU-SC baseline. An exception is observed with Dynamic Quantization (DYN), which performs significantly slower on the NPU. This inefficiency arises because the NPU lacks native support for the runtime data-type casting required by DYN. Consequently, these operations are offloaded to the CPU, incurring substantial data transfer overhead that negates the accelerator’s performance gains. This result confirms that the NPU is optimized for static, pre-calculated data rather than dynamic, runtime conversions.

Fig. 2: ResNet50 inference speeds across devices & quantizations

Focusing on CPU performance (see Table VIII), the analysis revealed that the multithreaded speed-up (CPU-MC, utilizing the 8 available cores) was significantly lower than expected. The highest acceleration was achieved with INT8 quantization, reaching a factor of 3,4 \times , which suggests that the asymmetric multicore architecture significantly limits scalability.

Table VIII: Multithreaded vs single threaded execution (ms) and speed-up in ResNet50

	CPU-SC	CPU-MC	Speed-up
FP32	126.4	61.2	2.1x
FP16	141.1	60.9	2.3x
INT8	45.3	13.4	3.4x
DYN	47.2	17.4	2.7x

On the GPU side, we observe that quantization hardly affects inference performance (see Table IX). Instead, the largest performance impact stems from the GPU’s operating mode (FP32 vs. FP16), resulting in speed-ups approaching 2 \times if the GPU is configured to operate as GPU16.

Table IX: GPU FP32 vs FP16 execution (ms) in ResNet50

	GPU32	GPU16
FP32	14.9	8.1
FP16	14.86	8.12
INT8	15.17	8.39
DYN	14.78	8.13

Table X presents the accuracy variations resulting from model quantization. Switching from single-precision (FP32) to half-precision (FP16) floating point has a negligible impact on accuracy, with variations remaining within $\pm 0,04\%$. In contrast, quantizing the model to integer (INT8) or dynamic formats leads to a more notable decline, although the maximum accuracy loss remains below 0,5%, demonstrating the robustness of the quantization process.

Table X: ResNet50 Top1 accuracy (%)

	CPU-SC	CPU-MC	GPU32	GPU16	NPU
FP32	79.09	79.09	79.06	79.09	79.1
FP16	79.1	79.1	79.1	79.06	79.1
INT8	78.68	78.73	78.68	78.68	78.77
DYN	78.9	78.91	78.9	-	78.94

The analysis of quantization impact reveals a clear correlation between model size and accuracy preservation. As shown in Table XI, the accuracy loss incurred by INT8 quantization decreases significantly as the model complexity increases (from 2.94% for ResNet18 down to $\leq 0.5\%$ for larger variants). This trend confirms that larger models mitigate the information loss associated with reduced data width due to their deeper feature extraction capabilities. In contrast, Dynamic Quantization (DYN) consistently introduces negligible loss.

Table XI: Summary of Top-1 Accuracy Loss by Quantization vs. FP32 (%)

Quant.	ResNet18	ResNet34	ResNet50	ResNet101	ResNet152
INT8	2.94%	0.50%	0.41%	0.01%	0.20%
DYN	0.10%	0.04%	0.19%	0.00%	0.07%

Furthermore, Table XII demonstrates that converting the original single-precision floating-point models from PyTorch to the LiteRT framework introduces an inherent accuracy loss, independent of any subsequent quantization. This discrepancy, ranging between 0.83% and 1.77%, suggests that variations in operation implementations and numerical precision handling across frameworks prevent a bit-exact conversion. This baseline degradation is a critical factor that must be decoupled from the accuracy loss specifically attributed to quantization.

Table XII: Precision lost (Top-1) due to framework conversion (LiteRT vs. PyTorch) (%)

Model	ResNet18	ResNet34	ResNet50	ResNet101	ResNet152
Lost	0.95%	0.83%	1.77%	1.16%	0.98%

B. YOLOv8

Results for the YOLOv8n model exhibit a performance pattern consistent with ResNet, where hardware accelerators (GPU and NPU) significantly reduce inference latency. As expected, YOLOv8n presents higher absolute latency compared to ResNet; this is attributed to the increased architectural complexity required for object detection versus the simpler requirements of image classification. Figure 3 illustrates these inference times across different devices and quantization levels. Notably, the NPU continues to provide the highest throughput, outperforming both the CPU and GPU, particularly when utilizing INT8 quantization.

Fig. 3: YOLOv8n inference speeds across devices & quantizations

Regarding accuracy, Table XIII reveals that integer-quantized variants experience more severe degradation compared to their ResNet counterparts. This significant drop in mAP suggests that object detection models, such as YOLOv8, are more sensitive to lower precision (INT8) due to the simultaneous demands of bounding box localization and object classification. In contrast, Dynamic Quantization (DYN) maintains high fidelity, with a negligible maximum loss of only 0.1 mAP across all models. Conversely, INT8 quantization leads to a substantial performance decline, with an average reduction of 6.5 mAP points, highlighting the trade-off between the NPU’s inference speed and model precision.

Table XIII: YOLOv8 accuracy loss (mAP) compared to FLOAT32 precision

Quant.	YOLOv8n	YOLOv8s	YOLOv8m	YOLOv8l	YOLOv8x
INT8	6.5	6.2	6.2	7.5	6.1
DYN	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1

C. YOLO11

With YOLO11 being an upgraded version of YOLOv8 it is expected to behave similarly but come with some improvements compared to its predecessor. The Figure 4 presents the newer YOLO11 inference times. It generally behaves like YOLOv8 but shows minor changes: CPU inference is slightly faster, while GPU speeds are nearly identical. Execution on the NPU is marginally slower for both float and INT8 models, and dynamic quantization fails to run entirely on the NPU. This performance shift is likely due to YOLO11’s more complex architecture and new layers compared to its predecessor.

Fig. 4: YOLO11n inference speeds across devices & quantizations

Accuracy results for YOLO11 follow the general trend observed in YOLOv8, as shown in Table XIV. However, integer quantization (INT8) induces a slightly more pronounced degradation in this architecture, with a mean accuracy loss of approximately 7.2 mAP across all variants. Notably, YOLO11 exhibits the most significant decline, reaching a loss of 8.7 mAP. Consistent with previous findings, Dynamic Quantization (DYN) maintains near-optimal fidelity, with a maximum loss of only 0.2 mAP. These results suggest that while YOLO11 offers architectural improvements, its internal weights and activations are more sensitive to the precision loss inherent in 8-bit integer mapping compared to the YOLOv8 family.

Table XIV: YOLO11 accuracy loss (mAP) compared to FLOAT32 precision

Quant.	YOLO11n	YOLO11s	YOLO11m	YOLO11l	YOLO11x
INT8	6.6	6.8	6.7	8.7	7.2
DYN	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.1

Finally, it is worth noting that YOLO11 exhibits a minor accuracy degradation when compared directly to its original PyTorch implementation. This loss, which ranges between 0.2 and 0.4 mAP points, is attributed to the framework conversion process into the LiteRT runtime environment. This suggests that the architectural innovations and novel layers introduced in YOLO11 pose a slightly greater challenge for bit-exact translation than previous iterations. Nevertheless, empirical evidence confirms that YOLO11 achieves superior overall FP32 accuracy across all model scales compared to YOLOv8, as illustrated in Figure 5. Consequently, YOLO11 stands as the more precise architecture for object detection tasks within the scope of this study.

Fig. 5: YOLO11 vs YOLOv8 accuracy comparison

V. DISCUSSION

Based on the comprehensive evaluation of all models across the available hardware, the NPU emerges as the most efficient accelerator. It achieves substantial speed-ups even for the smallest architectures, such as 47 \times for YOLOv8n and 130 \times for ResNet18. Notably, the performance advantage of the NPU scales with model complexity, reaching a peak speed-up of 298 \times for the YOLOv8x variant. Table XV summarizes these performance gains relative to the CPU-SC baseline. These results highlight that the NPU’s architectural advantages—specifically its ability to handle massive parallel integer arithmetic—are most effectively leveraged by deeper and wider neural networks.

Table XV: NPU execution speed-ups

		FP32	FP16	INT8	DYN
ResNet	18	65.9x	66.4x	129.6x	2.1x
	34	89.2x	88.2x	190x	3.7x
	50	54.3x	53.3x	121.5x	2.3x
	101	64.9x	63.6x	149.7x	3x
	152	70x	67.5x	164.1x	-
YOLOv8	n	29x	28.2x	46.8x	1.6x
	s	60.2x	60.5x	128.3x	2.9x
	m	77.6x	81.6x	209.4x	-
	l	99.5x	100.7x	277.6x	-
	x	98.2x	100x	298x	-
YOLO11	n	20.6x	20.8x	32.4x	-
	s	44.2x	41.5x	76.5x	-
	m	62.3x	64.9x	146.1x	-
	l	71.2x	72.5x	160.3x	-
	x	72.9x	72.6x	173.9x	-

Another key observation is the performance bottleneck associated with Dynamic Quantization (DYN) across all architectures. This method consistently yields lower speed-ups compared to other quantization variants and, in certain larger models, fails to execute on the NPU. This limitation is primarily due to the lack of native support for runtime casting, as previously discussed. Furthermore, the results demonstrate clear scalability: as model complexity increases, the NPU’s acceleration becomes more pronounced. This trend is particularly evident in the YOLOv8 family, where the transition from nano to extra-large scales maximizes the hardware’s compu-

tational throughput.

Regarding CPU performance, Table XVI illustrates that the speed-up achieved through multi-threading is predominantly driven by integer precision (INT8). While floating-point variants yield a modest $2\times$ to $3\times$ acceleration, INT8 consistently achieves a more significant $10\times$ to $15\times$ speed-up. Multi-threading efficiency, however, varies by architecture: ResNet models exhibit a diminishing speed-up in INT8 as model depth increases. In contrast, YOLO models demonstrate an opposite trend, leveraging multi-threading more effectively as they scale up, suggesting a more parallelizable workload in larger detection architectures.

Table XVI: Multithreaded execution speed-ups

		FP32	FP16	INT8	DYN
ResNet	18	3x	3x	14x	10.6x
	34	3.1x	3.1x	15.1x	12x
	50	2x	2x	9.5x	7.2x
	101	2.2x	2.1x	9.2x	7.2x
	152	2.2x	2.3x	9.4x	7.6x
YOLOv8	n	2.4x	2.4x	9.4x	4.6x
	s	2.3x	2.3x	11.1x	6.7x
	m	2.4x	2.4x	12.5x	7.5x
	l	2.3x	2.7x	12.8x	9.7x
	x	2.7x	2.1x	13.4x	10.1x
YOLO11	n	2.2x	2.2x	7.2x	3.1x
	s	2.1x	2.1x	10.4x	4.3x
	m	2.4x	2.3x	13.1x	6.2x
	l	2.6x	2.3x	13.4x	6.6x
	x	2.2x	2.1x	12.5x	7.3x

Finally, the analysis of GPU performance, presented in Table XVII, reveals that the highest speed-ups are achieved in GPU16 mode. In contrast to the CPU, variations in quantization precision (FP32, FP16, INT8, and DYN) have a marginal impact on the speed-up factor. This suggests that GPU performance is constrained by other factors, such as memory bandwidth or arithmetic complexity, rather than data-type precision alone. Nevertheless, FP16 often emerges as the optimal choice, providing an ideal balance between inference speed and accuracy.

Regarding scaling, YOLO models demonstrate superior efficiency on the GPU, with the largest variants reaching a peak acceleration of approximately $39\times$ (YOLOv8x). In comparison, ResNet models maintain a more consistent speed-up across all sizes. These results indicate that larger models leverage half-precision execution more effectively than smaller ones. This behavior aligns with standard GPU performance characteristics, where massively parallel workloads—typical of deeper and wider architectures—are required to fully saturate the device’s computational resources.

Table XVII: GPU16 execution speed-ups

		FP32	FP16	INT8	DYN
ResNet	18	17.5x	-	16.9x	-
	34	20x	20x	-	20x
	50	15.6x	15.6x	15.1x	15.6x
	101	15.8x	15.8x	15.5x	15.8x
	152	16.5x	16.5x	16.3x	16.3x
YOLOv8	n	8.5x	8.6x	8x	8.5x
	s	17.2x	17.1x	15.5x	17.1x
	m	14.6x	14.6x	13.1x	14.6x
	l	35x	34.8x	31.9x	34.9x
	x	38.3x	38.2x	34.8x	38.6x
YOLO11	n	6.8x	6.8x	6x	6.8x
	s	14x	14x	12.3x	14x
	m	23.2x	23.2x	19.3x	23.1x
	l	25.5x	25.2x	22x	25.2x
	x	30.1x	30.1x	26.5x	30.2x

Beyond individual metric analysis, selecting the optimal configuration is inherently challenging due to conflicting objectives, such as maximizing accuracy while minimizing inference latency and power consumption. To address this multi-criteria decision problem, a multi-objective optimization approach based on Pareto Front analysis is proposed. To maintain visual clarity, only FP16 and INT8 quantizations are displayed, as they represent the most competitive configurations for deployment.

Figures 6 and 7 illustrate the resulting Pareto Fronts, showcasing the non-dominated trade-offs between accuracy and latency. For the ResNet family (Figure 6), INT8 quantization emerges as the superior choice; the substantial reduction in latency effectively compensates for the marginal decline in Top-1 accuracy, placing these variants closer to the ideal bottom-right corner of the objective space. In contrast, for the YOLO models (Figure 7), the significant accuracy degradation associated with integer precision shifts the INT8 variants away from the optimal front. In the case of object detection, the trade-off is more polarized, requiring designers to carefully prioritize either extreme throughput (INT8) or high detection fidelity (FP16).

Fig. 7: Frente Pareto YOLO11

An additional takeaway is that YOLO11 tends to outperform YOLOv8 primarily in the smaller model scales (nano and small), where the substantial gain in accuracy justifies the marginal increase in inference latency. However, this relative advantage diminishes as the model size scales up. In the larger variants (large and extra-large), the accuracy gap between the two architectures narrows, while the latency overhead becomes more pronounced, resulting in a less favorable performance-to-cost ratio for the latest iteration.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper evaluated the performance of ResNet and YOLO models for image classification and object detection, respectively, across three devices (CPU, GPU, NPU) and four precisions in an Android tablet. The key findings are:

- **NPU Dominance:** The NPU emerged as the superior execution device, achieving speed-ups of up to 298× for large-scale detection models (YOLOv8x) compared to the single-core CPU baseline. This confirms the NPU’s essential role in enabling real-time, low-latency edge AI.
- **Optimal Quantization Trade-offs:** The choice between FP16 and INT8 is model-dependent:
 - For ResNet, INT8 is the optimal precision, as its performance gains on the NPU and multi-threaded CPU significantly outweigh its negligible accuracy loss.
 - Conversely, for GPU execution, quantization yields marginal benefits, making FP16 the preferred choice to preserve full accuracy without sacrificing speed.
- **Architecture Scaling:** YOLO11 exhibits a superior accuracy-to-latency ratio in smaller model scales (nano and small) compared to YOLOv8. However, this advantage diminishes in larger variants where increased architectural complexity results in higher latency overhead.
- **System Limitations:** Critical performance

bottlenecks were identified.

- Dynamic Quantization (DYN) proved inefficient on the NPU due to a lack of native support for runtime casting.
- Furthermore, while CPU multi-threading provides notable gains ($\approx 3,4\times$ max speed-up) for INT8, scalability is constrained by the platform’s asymmetric core architecture.

The results further reveal a clear correlation between model occupancy and accelerator efficiency. Smaller models (e.g., Nano and Small variants) appear to be memory-bound, failing to fully saturate the NPU and GPU computational units. In contrast, larger architectures effectively leverage the massively parallel nature of these accelerators, as evidenced by the exponential growth in speed-up factors. Additionally, the poor performance of Dynamic Quantization on the NPU underscores a critical hardware-software mismatch: while DYN offers flexibility, the lack of dedicated hardware for runtime data-type casting makes static INT8 quantization the only viable path for high-efficiency edge deployment.

As future work, we plan to integrate power consumption metrics into the Pareto analysis to finalize a tri-objective optimization (accuracy, latency, and energy efficiency). Additionally, we intend to investigate methods to mitigate the $\approx 1\%$ accuracy loss observed during framework conversion and extend this benchmark to the MLPerf suite, including tasks such as natural language processing and image segmentation.

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